

ASSESSMENT OF PSYCHOSOCIAL HEALTH PROBLEMS AMONG PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN DELTA SOUTH SENATORIAL DISTRICT, DELTA STATE.

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Abstract: Teachers' psychosocial and mental health are critical determinants of their effectiveness and overall well-being in the workplace. This study assessed the extent to which public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems and psychosocial health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive cross-sectional survey design. The population comprised 1,862 public secondary school teachers, from which a sample of 500 teachers was selected using the Taro Yamane formula. A multi-stage sampling procedure involving purposive, systematic, and simple random sampling techniques was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire validated by experts, with a reliability coefficient of 0.82 obtained through the Pearson Product Moment Correlation method. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while z-test and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that teachers experience mental health problems to a high extent (grand mean = 2.99), with common issues including depression, headache, aggressiveness, and loss of concentration. Similarly, psychosocial health problems were experienced to a high extent (grand mean = 3.05), with anger, confusion, and emotional instability identified as prevalent concerns. The study concluded that public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District experience high levels of mental and psychosocial health problems. It was recommended that targeted interventions, supportive work environments, and structured coping strategies be implemented to enhance teachers' psychological and social well-being.

Introduction

Psychosocial health problems among public secondary school teachers are increasingly influenced by workplace and occupational

conditions) within the school environment. Teaching, though widely regarded as a noble profession, is psychosocially demanding and characterized by heavy workloads, overcrowded

classrooms, poor work environments, and complex interpersonal interactions, all of which predispose teachers to various health challenges (Dreer & Gouasé, 2022; Cherkowski & Walker, 2018). The school environment, administrative structure, job demands, and available support systems significantly shape teachers' psychological and social well-being (Dicke et al., 2018).

Mental health, which encompasses emotional, psychological, and behavioral functioning, is fundamental to effective teaching and overall job performance (Travers, 2017). Evidence indicates that excessive workload, delayed salaries, poor promotion prospects, overcrowded classrooms, and student deviant behaviors contribute to depression, emotional exhaustion, anxiety, irritability, and loss of concentration among teachers (Buonomo et al., 2017). Chronic exposure to these occupational stressors may result in burnout and reduced professional effectiveness. Ji et al. (2021) reported that mental health conditions among teachers are significantly associated with occupational stressors, particularly workload and poor organizational climate. Similarly, Sakellari et al. (2021) emphasized that sustained psychological strain in the workplace compromises teachers' productivity and overall well-being.

Psychosocial health, which reflects individuals' ability to maintain healthy social relationships and cope effectively with workplace demands, is equally affected by occupational conditions in schools. Teachers frequently encounter psychosocial hazards such as verbal abuse, workplace bullying, inadequate social support, large class sizes, and strained staff–student relationships (Bernotaite & Malinauskiene, 2017). These stressors may manifest in anger,

confusion, emotional instability, and impaired interpersonal functioning. It was observed that teachers exposed to poor organizational support and limited promotion opportunities were significantly more likely to experience psychosocial health challenges. Deguchi et al. (2018) further found that social support from supervisors and colleagues plays a crucial moderating role in reducing psychosocial distress among teachers.

In the Nigerian context, particularly in Delta State, public secondary schools often operate under challenging conditions, including overcrowding due to free education policies, inadequate instructional materials, and poor infrastructural facilities. These environmental and organizational deficiencies expose teachers to sustained occupational stress, which adversely affects both mental and psychosocial health outcomes (Arop et al., 2018). The World Health Organization (2020) underscores that workplace environments significantly determine employees' psychological well-being, stressing the need for systemic interventions to safeguard workers' mental and social health.

Despite the recognized importance of teachers in achieving educational goals, limited empirical attention has been given to the specific extent of mental and psychosocial health problems experienced by public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. Existing literature has largely focused on general occupational hazards without sufficiently isolating the psychological and social dimensions of health in relation to teachers' workplace experiences. This gap necessitates a focused assessment of the extent to which teachers experience mental and psychosocial health problems within the study area.

In view of the foregoing, this study concentrates specifically on examining the extent to which public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District experience mental health problems and psychosocial health problems as influenced by occupational and workplace conditions in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State.

Objectives of this Study

The aim of this study is to assess the extent to which occupational and workplace conditions influence mental and psychosocial health problems among public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria. In specific terms, this study sought to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta south Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.
2. Identify the extent to which public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems in Delta south Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were answered in the study.

1. To what extent do public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria?
2. To what extent do public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

In regards to this study, the following null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the extent of experience of mental health problems between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the extent of experience of psychosocial health problems among public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of

Research Design

The study adopted the descriptive cross sectional survey design which is aimed at collecting data and describing it in a systematic manner the characteristics, features and information about teacher in the senior secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. A descriptive survey design is concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual group within a specific period in of time. Elendu (2010) asserted that descriptive design is the type of survey design that generates data from a selected population explaining and describing events as they occur in their natural setting at a particular time.

Population of the Study: The population of the study consisted of all secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State which was one thousand eight hundred and sixty two (1862) secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District, Delta State (Delta State Post Primary Education Board, 2023).

Sample size: The sample size for this study consisted of 500 public secondary school teachers drawn from Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane formula for sample size determination at a 0.05 level of precision. In addition, a 25% allowance was added to accommodate possible non-response,

thereby increasing the calculated sample to 500 respondents.

A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed. In the first stage, the eight Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Delta South Senatorial District were purposively considered as the study area. In the second stage, systematic sampling technique was used to select four LGAs from the eight. In the third stage, simple random sampling technique was adopted to select twenty (20) public secondary schools (five schools from each selected LGA). Finally, twenty-five (25) teachers were randomly selected from each of the twenty selected schools to make up the total sample of 500 respondents.

Instrument for Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Occupational Health Problems and Safety Strategies Questionnaire (OHPSSQ). However, for the purpose of this study, only items relating to mental health problems and psychosocial health problems were utilized. The instrument was structured on a four-point modified Likert scale of Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1).

Validity of the Instrument: The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by three experts in Human Kinetics, Health and Safety Studies. Their corrections, suggestions,

and recommendations were incorporated into the final version of the questionnaire to ensure that it adequately measured the variables under study.

Reliability of the Instrument: The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test–retest method. The questionnaire was administered to 20 teachers outside the study area. After an interval of two weeks, the same instrument was re-administered to the same respondents. The data obtained were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC), which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.82, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to answer the research questions, while inferential statistics (z-test and Analysis of Variance – ANOVA) were employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The various data collected from respondents in the study were presented under the following tables based on the research questions and hypotheses generated.

Demographic Analysis

Table 1: Summary of Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (n = 500)

Variable	Option	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Age	25–34 years	72	14.4
	35–44 years	180	36.0
	45–54 years	189	37.8
	55–64 years	59	11.8
Gender	Male	215	42.9

Marital Status	Female	285	56.9
	Married	362	72.4
	Unmarried	138	27.6
Location	Urban	294	58.8
	Rural	206	41.2
Work Experience	2–10 years	138	27.6
	11–19 years	186	37.2
	20–29 years	167	33.4
	30–39 years	9	1.8
Educational Qualification	M.Ed	78	15.6
	PGDE	39	7.8
	B.Sc (Ed)	371	74.2
	NCE	12	2.4
Job Training	Yes	308	61.6
	No	192	38.4

The demographic distribution shows that the majority of respondents were within the age bracket of 45–54 years (37.8%), followed closely by those aged 35–44 years (36.0%), indicating a relatively mature and experienced teaching workforce. Female teachers (56.9%) were more than male teachers (42.9%), suggesting female dominance in public secondary schools within the study area. A large proportion of the respondents were married (72.4%), which may have implications for work–family balance and psychosocial stress factors. More teachers were located in urban schools (58.8%) compared to rural schools (41.2%). In terms of work experience, most teachers had between 11–19 years of experience (37.2%), followed by 20–29 years (33.4%), indicating that the majority of respondents were experienced professionals.

Regarding educational qualification, most teachers held a B.Sc (Ed) degree (74.2%), while only a small proportion possessed NCE certificates (2.4%). Finally, a greater percentage of respondents (61.6%) had undergone job training, suggesting that most teachers had received some form of professional development, although a considerable proportion (38.4%) had not received retraining. Overall, the data reflect a predominantly experienced, professionally qualified, and urban-based teaching population in Delta South Senatorial District.

Research Questions 1:

To what extent do public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of descriptive analysis of the extent public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta south Senatorial District

Mental Health Problems	Mean	Std. Dev.
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1	Long teaching periods make teachers to experience headache	2.79	0.97
2	Teachers experience depression in the school when salaries and allowances are not paid	3.25	0.69
3	The school environment makes teachers to be aggressive when they interact with others	3.15	0.58
4	Over crowded nature of classrooms makes teachers to loose concentration in the school	3.11	0.66
5	The unfriendly nature of the school environment makes teachers to suffer from psychological health problems	2.68	0.87
	Grand Mean	2.99	0.75

Grand Mean = 2.99; Criterion Mean: 2.50; Extent = High

Table 9 reveals the mental health problems of teachers in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State. From the Data presented and analyzed in the table, it was discovered that all the observed mean value (2.79, 3.25, 3.15, 3.11 & 2.68) with standard deviation of 0.97, 0.69, 0.58, 0.66 & 0.87) respectively were higher than the criterion mean of 2.5. This indicated that headache, depression, aggressiveness, loss of concentration in the school and psychological health problems were common mental health problems of teachers in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District.

From the grand mean analysis, it was revealed that the observed grand mean (2.99) was higher than the criterion mean value (2.5) at 4-point scale indicating high extent. This means that the extent public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria is high.

Research Question 2: To what extent do public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of descriptive analysis on the extent public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems among secondary school teachers in Delta south Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria

	Psychosocial health problems	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Teachers are prone to anger	3.24	0.72
2	Uncontrolled classroom student population size leave teachers in a state of confusion	3.47	0.30
3	Teachers experience anxiety due to the excessive workload they have to accomplish in the school	2.37	0.97
4	Students deviant behaviour in the school cause teachers to experience lack of coherence	2.87	0.90

5	Teachers experience mental health problems because of the demands of attention from a large number of students in the school.	3.31	1.45
Grand Mean		3.05	0.87

Grand Mean = 3.05; Criterion Mean: 2.50; Extent = High

Table 3 reveals the psychosocial health problems teachers face in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. From the data presented and analyzed, it was found item 26, 27, 29 & 30 with mean value of 3.24, 3.47, 2.87 & 3.31 and standard deviation of 0.72, 0.30, 0.90 & 1.45 respectively were higher than the criterion mean value of 2.5. This means that prone to anger, state of confusion, lack of coherence and mental health problems were psychosocial health problems of teachers in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. It was however found that anxiety due to the excessive workload they have to accomplish in the school which have a mean of 2.37 that was less than the 2.5 criterion

mean was not a psychosocial health problems of teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. From the grand mean analysis, it was revealed that the observed grand mean (3.05) was higher than the criterion mean value (2.5) at 4-point scale indicating high extent. This means that the extent public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria is high.

Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the extent of experience of mental health problems between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.

Table 4: z-test analysis of diff. in the extent of experience of mental health problems between married and unmarried public secondary school teachers

Variables	N	Mean	SD	z-cal	z-crit	df	Sig	Decision
Urban	294	8.88	16.71					
Rural	206	6.07	13.96	2.03	1.96	498	0.05	Rejected

The table 4 revealed the z-test analysis of the extent of experience of mental health problems between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. From the z-test analysis, it was found that z-calculated value (2.03) was higher than the z-critical value (1.96) under degree of freedom 498 at 0.05 significant. Thus the null hypothesis stated was rejected. This means that there is significant difference in the extent of

mental health problems experienced between urban and rural public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the extent of experience of psychosocial health problems among public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria based on qualification.

Table 5: Summary of ANOVA analysis on the extent of experience of psychosocial health problems among secondary school teachers in Delta South senatorial district of Delta State based on qualifications.

ANOVA

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	4.875	2	2.437	16.056	.000
Within Groups	67.684	496	.147		
Total	78.011	499			

Table 12 reveals the summary of ANOVA analysis on occupational health problems among secondary school teachers in Delta South senatorial district of Delta State based on job training. The table revealed that $F_{(500, 2)} = 16.056$ at 0.000 significance level. Since, the level of significant is less than 0.05, then the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the extent of experience of psychosocial health problems among public secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria based on qualification.

Discussion of Findings

Extent of Mental health problems experienced by Teachers

The results from the study on mental health problems teachers’ revealed that the extent public secondary school teachers experience mental health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria is high (2.99). It was revealed that the extent public secondary school teachers experience occupational health in Delta South senatorial district of Delta State based on qualification is very high (3.09). This showed that teachers are exposure to mental health problems was high. It was found that headache, depression,

aggressiveness, loss of concentration in the school and psychological health problems were common mental health problems of teachers in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. It is pertinent to note that the process of teaching students at secondary school level constitute stress from managing from adolescent deviant behaviour in the classroom. The behavioural approaches of students in the classroom are likely to inflict mental ill-health such as depression, anxiety, burnout, low self-esteem among others. This finding is in line with Ji et al. (2021) analysis of the occupational health problems that affect teachers. Ji et al. (2021) stated that mental health was significantly associated with occupational health challenges ($p < 0.05$). Sakellari et al. (2021) added that effective mental health is more likely to improve good occupational health status of workers in the workplace especially teachers. Adzakpah et al. (2018) illustrated that teachers who are working in school with few numbers of workers are 3.44 times more likely to report any form of mental health problems except there an intervention. Bernotaite and Malinauskiene (2017) in their study noted that teaching in both public and private secondary schools can

inflict occupational burnout, high emotional exhaustion that affect the extent of achievement of teachers and good proportion of teachers who have verbal bullying from their students are in likelihood of been mentally unstable. Previously, Wuet al. (2006) in their reiterated that teachers are more likely to encounter mental health problems if they are exposed to work overload, interpersonal strain, too much responsibility and poor physical environment among others. It is plausible that secondary school students are likely to cause irritation and a lot of deviant behaviours in the classroom and within the school environment which has a negative fixation on the well-being of the teachers. The school environment as an academic challenging workplace poses occupational risks and problems that may affect quality service delivery. Social health provides the teachers with the ability to interrelate and communicate effectively among others in the environment.

Psychosocial Health Problems and Teachers Experience.

Findings from the study on psychosocial problems shows that the extent public secondary school teachers experience psychosocial health problems in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State, Nigeria is high (3.05). It was found that proneness to anger, state of confusion, lack of coherence and mental health problems were psychosocial health problems of teachers in public secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. The result of this study is required because social health provides the teachers with the ability to interrelate and communicate effectively among others in the environment. That is, since teaching is a stressful occupation, it directly or indirectly affects the social health of the

teachers. The result of this study is in agreement with findings of Bernotaite and Malinauskiene (2017) which reported that good proportion of teachers (59.6%) who experience low social support at the workplace are more likely to socially unhealthy. The school environment is social place were both teachers and students exhibit common relationship and communication. It was revealed that the extent to which public secondary school teachers experience occupational health in Delta South senatorial district of Delta State based on location is very high (3.16 > 2.5). Teachers' health status is greatly influenced by comfortable, healthy and happy conditions resulting into quality service delivery. According to American Federation of Teachers (2017), good proportion of teachers (61%) find their work stressful and unhealthy when there is work overload, poor human relationship among colleagues leading to feelings of irritation, difficulty in concentration and absenteeism. Adzakpah et al. (2018) revealed that teachers who are faced with lack of opportunity and work promotion are 2.78 times more likely to suffer social occupational health problems. Similarly, Deguchi et al. (2018) indicated that teachers who received social support for supervisors were significantly associated with gender, work experience and training. Gheshlagh et al. (2017) in their study buttressed that the prevalence of social health challenges was high among teachers who report work stress. Reflectively, Amadi and Achalu (2021) in their study concluded that secondary school teachers in Rivers State are exposed to physical and psychosocial occupational health risks which make them vulnerable to health problems associated with such exposure. Psychosocial hazards or risk reported among

the teachers in their workplace are workplace violence and bullying; working with students who require accommodations or assistance, internet harassment, workplace stress, and fatigue.

Conclusion

In regards to this study, it was concluded that teachers' public secondary schools to high extent are exposed to physical, mental and psychosocial health problems. The extent of their exposure and experience of different occupational health problems varies based on marital status, age, gender and work experience. From the finding of the study, it can be inferred that there are safety strategies which when teachers adopt will help to reduce their level of exposure to occupational health risk which daily affect their health. There is therefore need to provide teachers with occupational strategies to improve and promote good working environment to enhance job

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productivity and health status of the teachers in general.

Recommendations

Regarding this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since the extent teachers experience physical health problems is high, teachers should be provided with all necessary facilities, equipment and motivation by government and school management that can enable them ease their physical stress.
2. Teachers should be taught proper planning and stress coping strategies to enable them reduce their mental health stress and problems at work.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to maintain cordial, proper and effective staff-staff and staff – student's relationship to help them reduce their level of psychosocial problems and stress they experienced at work.

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